

ECC CONDITION ENHANCES ORGANIZATIONAL EXCELLENCE

Dr. Balaji D¹, Mr. Sripathi², K & Dr. B.R. Londhe³

¹Assistant Professor, ³Deputy Director & Professor, SIBM-H, SIU, Hyderabad, (India)

²Assistant Professor, DMS, Vignan's University, Guntur, (India)

ABSTRACT

A social unit of people which is systematically & scientifically structured and managed to meet a need or to pursue collective goals is encompassed as Organization. All organizations have a management structure that determines relationships between the different activities and the members, and subdivides and assigns roles, responsibilities, and authority to carry out different tasks. Emotional intelligence, also known as EI, is the innate ability of a person to perceive, assess, and influence one's own emotion and the emotions of other people around them. EQ principles provide a new way to understand and assess people's behaviors, management styles, attitudes, interpersonal skills, and potential, convincingly. Emotional Intelligence is an important consideration in human resources management. Organizational culture is therefore to an organization what personality is to an individual. "Organizational commitment" indicates that this construct which can be described from an attitudinal, behavioral and motivational perspective in an organization. This paper amalgamates the parameters entrusted by the above said three philosophies of organization and derived "The ECC Condition" which states the features of EI, Organizational Culture and Organizational Commitment, to facilitate an organization to sustain, out of which falls the prime stipulated state of "Organizational Excellence".

Keywords: *Emotional Intelligence, Organizational Culture, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Excellence.*

I. INTRODUCTION

An organization is a common platform where individuals from different backgrounds come together and work as a collective unit to achieve certain objectives and targets. The word organization derived from the Greek work "organon" is a set up where people join hands to earn a living for themselves as well as earn profits for the company. An organization consists of individuals with different specializations, educational qualifications and work experiences all working towards a common goal. Here the people are termed as employees. The employees are the major assets of an organization and contribute effectively in its successful functioning. It is essential for the employees to be loyal towards their organization and strive hard in furthering its brand image. An organization can't survive if the employees are not at all serious about it and treat their work as a burden. The employees must enjoy whatever they do for them to deliver their level best. A social unit of people which is systematically & scientifically structured and managed to meet a need or to pursue collective goals is encompassed as Organization. All organizations have a management structure that determines relationships between the different activities and the members, and subdivides and assigns roles, responsibilities, and

authority to carry out different tasks. Organizations are open systems--they affect and are affected by their environment. The process of organizing, planning, leading and controlling resources within an entity with the overall aim of achieving its objectives declares the notion of organizational management. In a defined business, it needs to be able to make decisions and resolve issues in order to be both effective and efficient for beneficial propagation. Understanding organization challenges is at the heart of successful strategic plans. There are challenges everywhere both within and outside the organizational boundaries. Clarity of challenges enables an organization to assess probability of achieving goals, and formulating plans to remove the road blocks on the way, identifying latent opportunities in the challenges – challenges are a pack of hidden opportunities. This journey is primarily an ontological journey – a journey that explores the nature of reality. The outcome of this journey is the discovery that emotional intelligence and organizational commitment of individuals and the organizational culture they do maintain in the organization consistently plays a primary role in reality construction. Hence, the journey to organizational excellence is an inside job. It begins with a paradigm shift in the management arena; however, lasting success is contingent upon a majority of stakeholders learning to “change their minds.” Thus enabling them to actually see, think, feel, act, trust, and are in profoundly new ways.

II. ORGANIZATIONAL EXCELLENCE

Organizational excellence is difficult to define and even more difficult to achieve. Whether excellence is defined as profitability, market share, customer/employee satisfaction, or product innovation, it is commonly sought by leaders, but rarely found. Yet, twenty-first-century leaders continue to search for excellence like knights of yore searching for the Holy Grail, experimenting with change processes in an oft never-ending sequence of flavor-of-the-month interventions. During the course of the past two decades Quality Circles, Self-Directed Work Teams, Total Quality Management, Process Improvement, and Reengineering have been frequently used by leaders in their attempts to create excellence. Though each of these interventions has value, none of them have proven to be a direct path to excellence. All of them focus on changing the organization – its people, processes, or products. None of them focus on changing the leader’s basic way of being – his or her worldview. This article purports that organizational excellence is an inside job. It is primarily the result of an internal paradigm shift – a shift that occurs first in the minds of the leaders, eventually permeating the minds of a critical mass of organizational stakeholders. The foundational premise of this belief, grounded in postmodern philosophy, is the idea that organizations are social constructions which mirror the collective beliefs of the stakeholders – beliefs about what it is possible to achieve (i.e., beliefs about excellence). Contemporary leadership theories and practices are essentially by-products of cultural modernism. Most twenty-first century leaders are unfamiliar with postmodern philosophy and its corresponding leadership implications. Society in general and business schools in particular, still espouse objectivity and rationality, the basic tenets of cultural modernism. However, from the postmodern perspective, it is impossible to determine the existence of an objective reality; hence, rationality is viewed as a function of cultural tradition.

III. EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

Emotional intelligence, as defined by Goleman, is the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in our relationships. His framework has five

branches: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Self-awareness is, knowing what one is feeling at the moment, and using those feelings in decision making, which is generally known as intuition or gut feelings that allows one to make decisions congruent with his or her deepest values. Self-awareness also involves having a realistic assessment of one's abilities. People who have this strength are aware of their strengths and weaknesses, open to candid feedback from others, and willing to learn from past experiences. Self-confidence is the courage that comes from certainty, through self-awareness, about our capabilities, values and goals. Handling our emotions such that they facilitate rather than interfere with tasks requires self-regulation. This manifests itself largely through the absence of disruptive emotional outbursts. Being conscientious and delaying gratification to pursue goals is another form of self-regulation. In a study by Mischel, et al. (1990), four-year-olds were given the choice of having a marshmallow now, or waiting a while later before getting two marshmallows instead. Fourteen years later, those who had resisted temptation and waited were more socially competent (being more self-assertive and better able to handle stress) than those who did not wait. In addition, those who waited had SAT scores 210 points higher than those who did not wait. Motivation is the emotional tendency that guides or facilitates reaching goals. It helps one to take initiative and strive for improvement and perseverance in the face of setbacks and frustrations. The need to achieve is the single strongest competence that distinguishes outstanding from average executives (Spencer and Spencer, 1993). Individuals with a high level of motivation readily make a realistic assessment of a setback and admit how they contributed to it rather than adopt a defeatist attitude. This is the ability to be aware of the feelings of others and to consider their perspective. People rarely tell us verbally what they feel. More often than not, we deduce what others are feeling about us through their subtle nonverbal signals such as tone of voice and facial expression. The ability to sense these signals builds on one's basic competencies, especially self-awareness and self-regulation. Moreover, empathy involves being able to cultivate a sense of rapport and attunement with people from diverse walks of life. People of different groups, regardless of gender, race or nationality, have their own norms of expressing emotions. To the extent that we are unfamiliar with these norms, empathizing becomes more difficult (Hall and Rosenthal, 1979). This involves handling emotions well in relationships and accurately reading social situations and networks, which are best demonstrated by diplomacy and tact. A person with good social skills will also be able to interact comfortably with others and persuade, lead, negotiate, and settle disputes for cooperation and teamwork. It is this adeptness at inducing desirable responses in others that makes them good leaders.

IV. ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE

Organizational culture is the behavior of humans within an organization and the meaning that people attach to those behaviors. Culture includes the organization's vision, values, norms, systems, symbols, language, assumptions, beliefs, and habits. It is also the pattern of such collective behaviors and assumptions that are taught to new organizational members as a way of perceiving, and even thinking and feeling. Organizational culture affects the way people and groups interact with each other, with clients, and with stakeholders. Social scientists have explored the notion of organizational culture as a perspective in organizational theory over the past decades. Martins and Martins (2003, p 380) state the general definition of organizational culture as "a system of shared meaning held by members, distinguishing the organization from other organizations". In

relation to the above definition, Arnold (2005, p 625) indicates that “organizational culture is the distinctive norms, beliefs, principles and ways of behaving that combine to give each organization its distinct character”. These two definitions suggest that organizational culture distinguishes one organization from another organization. Therefore, organizational culture is to an organization what personality is to an individual (Johnson, 1990). Linking up with the above definitions, Schein (1985, p 9) also defines organizational culture as “a pattern of basic assumptions invented, discovered, or developed by a given group as it learns to cope with its problems of external adaptation and internal integration that has worked well enough to be considered valid, and therefore, to be taught to new members as the correct way to perceive, think, and feel in relation to those problems”. This description highlights that organizational culture is created assumptions, which are accepted as a way of doing things and are passed on to new members of an organization. In relation to the above definition, Brown (1998, p 9) defines organizational culture as “the pattern of beliefs, values and learned ways of coping with experience that have developed during the course of an organization’s history, and which tend to be manifested in its material arrangements and in the behaviors of its members”. This suggests that organizational culture is articulated in the organization, in order to shape the way in which organizational members should behave. However, this pattern of values, norms, beliefs, attitudes, principles and assumptions may be unwritten or non-verbalized behavior that describes the way in which things get done; to give the organization its unique character (Brown, 1998). Given the various definitions of organizational culture which were discussed in this section, the adopted and relevant definition for this study is stated by Harrison (1993, p 11) denoted as the “distinctive constellation of beliefs, values, work styles, and relationships that distinguish one organization from another”. The culture gives the employees a sense of unity at the workplace. Certain organizations follow a culture where all the employees irrespective of their designations have to step into the office on time. Such a culture encourages the employees to be punctual which eventually benefits them in the long run. It is the culture of the organization which makes the individuals a successful professional. Every employee is clear with his roles and responsibilities and strives hard to accomplish the tasks within the desired time frame as per the set guidelines. Implementation of policies is never a problem in organizations where people follow a set culture. The new employees also try their level best to understand the work culture and make the organization a better place to work. The work culture promotes healthy relationship amongst the employees. The culture develops a habit in the individuals which makes them successful at the workplace. Culture represents the beliefs, ideologies, policies, practices of an organization. It gives the employees a sense of direction and also controls the way they behave with each other. The work culture brings all the employees on a common platform and unites them at the workplace. The very important factors those are identified by the review of literature of organizational culture are Goal, which further includes the mission, vision and value of the concern, the second is the Communication, which has its predominant importance and value as this becomes the nerve of the system running criss cross, third is the motivation & adaptability, which are the those that revamp the system, consistency is the one that establishes the formidability by performing and proving excellence continuously and finally the control, which is the ruler that gauges every move of the organization to the systematic standards which finally paves an effective and efficient attainment of the goal within determined time and quality.

V. ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

The concept organizational commitment include the description by O'Reilly (1989, p 17), "an individual's psychological bond to the organization, including a sense of job involvement, loyalty and belief in the values of the organization". Organizational commitment from this point of view is characterized by employee's acceptance of organizational goals and their willingness to exert effort on behalf of the organization (Miller & Lee, 2001). Cohen (2003, p xi) states that "commitment is a force that binds an individual to a course of action of relevance to one or more targets". This general description of commitment relates to the definition of organizational commitment by Arnold (2005, p 625) namely that it is "the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in an organization". Miller (2003: 73) also states that organizational commitment is "a state in which an employee identifies with a particular organization and its goals, and wishes to maintain membership in the organization". Organizational commitment is therefore the degree to which an employee is willing to maintain membership due to interest and association with the organization's goals and values. Various authors have discussed a possible theoretical link between organizational commitment and organizational culture. It appears as if organizational culture tends to influence employees' work effort and commitment directly through cultural values, and indirectly through human resources practices (Black 1999). Drenth, Thierry and Wolff (1998) found in their research a positive relationship between a high level of organizational commitment and the two dimensions of organizational culture – namely support-oriented culture and innovation-oriented culture. Findings by O'Reilly, Chatman & Caldwell (1991) suggest that individuals who fit the organizational culture are those who are committed at a normative or value-based commitment dimension; while Nystrom (1993) states that a correlation between organizational culture and organizational commitment indicates that people who work in a strong culture feel more committed. The concept organizational commitment has grown in popularity in the literature on industrial and organizational psychology (Cohen, 2003). Thus the key factors of organizational commitment are identified as affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment which are uniquely considered and enhanced for this conceptual derivation towards maintaining better effective & efficient organizational environment.

VI. AMALGAMATION OF ECC FACTORS FOR ORGANIZATIONS

From the above stated explanation of the concepts Emotional Intelligence, Organizational Culture and Organizational Commitment the factors of the same is been thoroughly analyzed and amalgamated to realize and justify a condition for any organization to better effective and efficient. The key factors of Emotional Intelligence are Interpersonal competencies and Intrapersonal competencies in major. To intervene into it deeply we identify self-awareness, self-regulation & self-motivation as intrapersonal competencies and interpersonal skills as empathy & social skill. Alike, organizational culture is been thoroughly analyzed to explore Goal, Communication, Motivation & Adaptability, Consistency and Control as its valid factors. Thus, organizational commitment is investigated to explore affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment as the key factors of the same.

JUSTIFICATION OF ECC CONDITION

A - Lacks in Continuous Motivation, Adaptability & Control

B - Lacks in Intra & Inter - Personal Competencies

C - Lacks in Commitment & Attainment

OE - Performance of Organizational Excellence Consistently

Figure 1 : Factors of ECC Condition

When a management of any organization, occur with any of the three main factors, which are emotional intelligence, organizational culture and organizational commitment in lacuna then effectiveness and efficiency of the organization starts to deteriorate and depreciate. Further, if any organization does have any of the two main factors then also the lacuna sustains with depreciative conditions in management and thus in organization. If an organization does have a good emotional intelligence and organizational culture then the factors of commitment and attainment urges diminishes which again doesn't let the organization towards attainment of its goal and objectives. If any organization has a good maintenance of better organizational culture and organizational commitment then the relationship management of interpersonal competencies and the intrapersonal competencies of the employee deteriorate to defective culture and lacuna in the personal and organizational commitment which directly affect the end results of any organization sustaining malfunction. If the emotional intelligence and the organizational commitment are maintained at a better level and the organizational culture is not sustained then the interpersonal & intrapersonal communication becomes ineffective further, the factors of motivation, adaptability and control will not occur in this sector which again propels ineffective environment of any organization, directly affecting driving instincts of employees. Apart from the above, when the organizational environment maintained with equal proportion of the three main factors mentioned, does better performance of employees abiding the organizational values towards attainment of organizational goals, which again includes individual goal attainment comfortably. Every organization is functioned core on people for people and when the people of any organization is supported with emotional,

cultural and commitment standard then the excellence of the organization becomes obvious at every time. In maintaining the ECC condition (Figure 1) the management with men, materiel and machine is made easy for effective and efficient accomplishment of selected aims. The interpersonal & intrapersonal competencies with relationship management combines with the goal, communication, motivational & adaptability, consistency and control factors of an organizational culture and again with the affective, continuance and normative commitment grounds do extremely well in performance of organizational excellence. At this juncture, it becomes evident that the organizational environment which sustains equal quantum of emotional intelligence, organizational culture and organizational commitment, which definitely excels in performance and attainment of both individual as well as organizational goals convincingly.

VII. CONSEQUENCE OF 5E – MADE EASY BY ECC CONDITION

If an organization is maintained at ECC condition the working environment propagates better results and the occurrence is not just once but this made as a characteristic habit of the system. The major consequence of ECC condition is stated and explained below:

- 1. Ease at work:** Productivity measures across national economies have captivated the attention of policy makers and executives alike. Ultimately, though, the source of productivity is the individual knowledge workers who get things done every day. And the evidence is clear when people perform better when they are happier and feel easy at work. Researches over the past decade have focused on creativity, productivity, and the psychology of everyday work life. Whether looked at entrepreneurial startups or large, established enterprises, the same holds true: People are more productive and creative when they have more positive emotions. In fact, it is found that, if happier on a given day, people were not only more likely to come up with a new idea or solve a complex problem that same day but also to do so the next day.
- 2. Error Minimization:** Customer demand for quality has continued to increase over the last several years. Pressure from emerging countries and knowledge provided by quality gurus like Deming, Juran, and Crosby have all contributed to this quality revolution. However, a large number of organizations still have not mastered the ability to eliminate errors without increasing costs, and often the problem lies not in how hard they try but in how they go about it. Companies that still consider quality to be an additive function instead of integrating the attainment of quality into their processes will continue to fall behind. Thus, error minimization is the dire need of the organizational endeavors.
- 3. Ever Evolving Environment:** Work is clearly evolving which means that we are seeing new technologies and behaviors enter our organizations. These new behaviors and technologies are largely being fueled by the consumer web and now organizations are struggling to adapt. Instead of the traditional hierarchical model, organizations are adopting a more flattened approach where anyone can speak with and interact with anyone else. There is no longer any justification for keeping people from interacting and engaging with each other because of their seniority level. New collaborative platforms are making this especially easy today. Thus ECC condition propagates this evolution in organizational environments.
- 4. Effectiveness:** Teams of people working together for a common purpose have been a centerpiece of human social organization ever since our ancient ancestors first banded together to hunt game, raise families, and defend their communities. Human history is largely a story of people working together in groups to explore,

achieve, and conquer. A variety of global forces unfolding over the last two decades, however, has pushed organizations worldwide to restructure work around teams, to enable more rapid, flexible, and adaptive responses to the unexpected. This shift in the structure of work has made team effectiveness a salient organizational concern. ECC condition emphasis effectiveness to organizations convincingly.

5. **Extended Efficiency:** Individuals need to achieve the assigned targets within the desired time frame. It is essential for employees to meet deadlines and deliver results on time. Employees need to get their work done on time to expect timely appraisals and appreciation from not only managers but also external clients. Being efficient does not mean that accomplishment of more work in less time, ignoring the quality of work. Never the quality is compromised. Employees need to concentrate on work not only to deliver results on time but also yield high quality output. An employee is said to be efficient only when he accomplishes assigned tasks on time, with minimum errors. One needs to produce quality work in minimum possible time not at once but in a continuous manner for an organization to excel. ECC condition paves way for this kind of efficiency working atmosphere uncompromisingly.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Organizational excellence is not an event that occurs unknowing at sometimes; rather, it is a predetermined event that can happen at every time with the ECC condition that has been comprehensively explained as above, with the required parameters of the unique features of emotional intelligence, organizational culture and organizational commitment factors. Thus, this paper has considered all the required aspects of an organization and convincingly proposed ECC condition for organizational excellence attainment continuously.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abbasi, H., Abbasi, H., Faraji, A & Hajirasouliha, M. (2014). Investigating the effects of organizational culture on brand promise. *Management Science Letters* , 4(5), 1039-1042.
- [2] Bani, M., Yasoureini, M & Mesgarpour, A. (2014). A study on relationship between employees' psychological empowerment and organizational commitment. *Management Science Letters*, 4(6), 1197-1200.
- [3] Chehrazi, S & Shakib, M. (2014). A study on the relationship between emotional intelligence, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior. *Management Science Letters* , 4(6), 1103-1106.
- [4] Denison, D. R., & Spreitzer, G. M. (1991). Organizational culture and organizational development: A competing values approach. *Research in organizational change and development*, 5(1), 1-21.
- [5] Kim, W. G., Leong, J. K., & Lee, Y. K. (2005). Effect of service orientation on job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and intention of leaving in a casual dining chain restaurant. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 24(2), 171-193.
- [6] Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human resource management review*, 1(1), 61-89.